

Hybrid Semicrystalline-Amorphous Thermoplastic Composites for Aeronautical Applications

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Abstract. Processing of semi-crystalline thermoplastic matrix composites for aeronautical applications experienced some problems for the high temperatures required and for the need to control the cooling rate, in order to obtain the correct crystallinity content in the final product. The approach of processing the material in the amorphous state would allow lower processing temperatures, but the crystallization isn't satisfactory (cold crystallization). A new approach, based on hybrid semicrystalline-amorphous thermoplastic composites has been considered, potentially overcoming the mentioned problem, and the main issues of this concept are described. The approach is presently under investigation in a multinational research program supported by the European Commission (NHYTE).

Keywords: Composites, Thermoplastics, Aeronautics, Semi-crystalline, Amorphous, Hybrid, Out of Autoclave.

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INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composites for aeronautical applications are showing a continuous growing trend, and some recent large airliners, e.g. Boeing 787 and Airbus A350, have been performed with an amount of composite materials in the primary structures above 50%. Compared with thermosetting matrix composites the ones with thermoplastic matrix offer several potential advantages: they are tough, don't require refrigerated transport and storage, have unlimited storage life, can be welded and recycled and generally show high thermal stability and good fire resistance properties. But, despite of that, and despite of the growing applications of thermoplastics, mainly for interior and secondary parts, thermosetting resins are by far the preferred ones for primary applications. This is mainly due to the high processing temperatures required by the thermoplastic resins considered suitable for aeronautical applications (table 1), having a high T_g , if amorphous, and a high T_m (melting temperature of the crystalline phase) if semi-crystalline. Consequently processing costs are generally high, both for the prepreg production phase, causing high costs of the raw materials, and for the part production phase.

TABLE (1). Glass transition and melting temperatures of thermoplastic resins considered as matrix for composites for aeronautical applications

Thermoplastic Resin	Morphology	T_g , °C	T_m , °C
PEI	Amorphous	200	
PPS	Semi-Crystalline	85 - 90	275 - 290
PEEK	Semi-Crystalline	140 - 145	334 - 343

Thus, the affordability of thermoplastic composite parts depends on the possibility to utilize processes which are peculiar of thermoplastics, like thermoforming (with different options, including continuous compression molding), or technologies developed for thermoset composites, like Automated Fiber Placement (AFP), which can be more convenient if performed by thermoplastics (no curing required). In this work the processing of large parts made by thermoplastic based composite will be discussed, namely the issues related to AFP and autoclave processing, including comparison with thermosets.

COMPOSITE HAND LAY-UP AND AUTOCLAVING

The process utilized to manufacture most of the aeronautical structure is hand lay-up plus autoclaving of thermoset matrix prepregs. Uncured prepregs are laid-up to create a stacking, utilizing also their property to stick-up one on the other (tackiness). The lay-up was in the past performed by hand (hand lay-up); presently there is a growing automatization, and lay up is often performed by machines (automated lay-up). For surfaces with curvature specific machines are utilized which use narrow tapes (slits) that allow to follow the curved surfaces; this technique is named AFP (Automated Fiber Placement). Then the material is transformed utilizing a temperature cycle, which in the first moment creates flow, and then promotes polymerization; the temperature cycle is associated with a pressure cycle, in order to obtain a consolidation of the stacking during the cure. For this goal autoclaves are utilized, which are facilities able to give pressure together with heating. An example of cure and temperature cycle is reported in figure 1; a viscosity curve, describing a change of viscosity of the resin during the cycle, with a decrease of viscosity due to the temperature increase, followed by a viscosity raise due to polymerization, is shown in figure 2.

FIGURE 1. Curing cycle of thermoset (epoxy) composites

FIGURE 2. Typical viscosity curve of epoxy resin during the cure heating

There are two major differences by the processing point of view between the thermoplastic matrix prepregs and the thermosetting one:

- thermoplastics are already polymerized and consequently a time to complete the polymerization isn't required, with potentially shorter cycles. It is only necessary to reach a temperature above T_g for the amorphous thermoplastics and above T_m for the semi-crystalline ones, and this temperature is generally very high (e.g. about 400 °C for PEEK); furthermore for semi-crystalline materials the cooling rate must be controlled
- being already polymerized, thermoplastics aren't tacky at room temperature, and lay-up requires a local heating facility (e.g. laser) in order to reach the above mentioned temperatures (above T_g or T_m).

THERMOSETS VS. SEMI-CRYSTALLINE THERMOPLASTICS RHEOLOGICAL BEHAVIOUR

Polymeric materials are characterized by a glass transition in the zone around the glass transition temperature T_g . Heating the material above T_g causes a transition. For thermoplastic amorphous material the transition is from glassy to liquid state, and the material above T_g can flow (fig. 3.a). For cross-linked thermosets the transition is from glassy to rubbery state; the material above T_g is more soft, but doesn't flow for the action of cross-links (three dimensional structure) and keeps its shape (Fig.3.b). For semi-crystalline thermoplastics a similar transition from glassy to rubbery state is observed, but the hindering to the flow is given in this case by the crystalline phase (Fig. 3.c).

Fig. 3.a

Fig. 3.b

Fig. 3.c

FIGURE 3. Typical Modulus vs Temperature curves for Amorphous Thermoplastics (Fig. 3.a), Thermosets (Fig. 3.b) and Semi-Crystalline Thermoplastics (Fig. 3.c)

That suggests an analogy between thermosets and semi-crystalline thermoplastics (ref. 1). A similar analogy can be observed in the isothermal curves of complex viscosity vs. time for thermosets and semi-crystalline thermoplastics compared in fig. 4a and 4b. In both cases a gelation is observed; for thermosetting gelation is induced by crosslinks; for semi-crystalline thermoplastics the curve is obtained starting by amorphous state, in which the material can flow, and the gelation is caused by crystallization (ref. 2,3).

Fig. 4.a

Fig. 4.b

FIGURE 4. Typical curves complex viscosity vs time at constant temperature for Thermosets (Fig. 4.a) and for and Semi-Crystalline Thermoplastics starting from amorphous state (Fig. 4.b)

These considerations suggest a method to overcome the processing problems caused by the need to work at high temperature for semi-crystalline thermoplastic. A theoretically feasible solution is to work with semi-crystalline thermoplastics in the amorphous state; that can be obtained by fast cooling, which doesn't allow the growth of crystals. A fabrication test was performed by Leonardo in cooperation with Novotech in a national research project; an Automated Fiber Placement machine was utilized to create a lay-up of PEEK-carbon fiber commercial composite, supplied with the matrix in the amorphous state. The prepreg tackiness, needed to allow the adhesion of the ply placed by the machine over the previously placed one, was obtained with a local heating performed by laser, and the lay-up was performed demonstrating the feasibility of the concept at a temperature above T_g but below T_m .

The utilization of laser also allowed a very fast heating, necessary to prevent a too fast gelation, due to the fast crystal nucleation and growth, which stops the flow. Some concerns exist about the quality of the product obtained with this approach; in fact the crystals obtained by crystallization from amorphous state above T_g (cold crystallization) show a morphology different from the one (spherulitic) obtained by cooling from melt, and the crystallinity content is lower than the one obtained for PEEK from melt and in the correct cooling rate window (about 33%).

THE AMORPHOUS-SEMICRYSTALLINE THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX PREPREG

A new concept was developed to keep the advantages of working on the amorphous state without negative effects on crystallinity: the amorphous-semicrystalline thermoplastic matrix prepreg. This is obtained by making a sandwich with a PEEK matrix carbon prepreg (APC-2) between two amorphous PEI films, and consolidating it in a process which gives full consolidation and controlled cooling rate, in order to obtain the right PEEK crystallinity (both amount and morphology). A sketch of the hybrid is shown in fig. 5.a along with some prototypes of panels obtained with the hybrid prepreg in fig. 5.b.

Fig. 5.a

Fig. 5.b

FIGURE 5. Sketch of hybrid amorphous semi-crystalline thermoplastic prepreg (Fig. 4.a) and optical microscopies of prototype panels made with the hybrid prepreg

The good integration of the two materials (PEEK and PEI) is obtained through a transition zone with different percentages of the two materials, progressively ranging from 100-0% to 0-100%, which is possible due to the capability of the two materials to make blends (ref. 4,5).

A multinational research program was activated aimed to develop: the hybrid prepreg manufacturing process; the panel fabrication process by Automated Fiber Placement and by low temperature autoclave; the fabrication of aeronautical structures assembled by welding. This research project, named NHYTE (New Hybrid Thermoplastic Composite Aerostructures manufactured by Out of Autoclave Continuous Automated Technologies) is in progress, supported by the European Commission.

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